

Integrated Farming system (IFS): An Interdependent, Interrelated and Interlocking production systems

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The IFS model combines various compatible enterprises such as crops (field crops, horticultural crops), agroforestry (agri-silvi culture, agri-horticulture, agri-pastoral, silvi-pastoral, horti-pastoral), livestock (dairy, pigs, poultry, small ruminants), fishery, mushroom and bee culture in a synergistic way so that the wastes of one process become the input for other processes for optimum farm productivity.

Setting up of IFS

In an IFS model, the field crops are grown for food production. Horticultural and vegetable crops can also provide 2-3 times more energy production than cereal crops and hence ensure nutritional security and income sustainability in the same piece of land. The crop residues after harvesting can be used for animal feed for dairy and goat production. The animal excreta from the animals can also be utilized as organic fertilizer or vermicomposting which in turn improves the soil fertility and thereby, reduces the use of chemical fertilizers. Again, the animal excreta can be dried, composted or liquid composted for the production of biogas and energy for household use. Integrated farming systems fulfill the multiple objectives of making farmers self-sufficient by ensuring the family members a balance diet, improving the standard of living through maximizing the total net returns and provide more employment, minimizing the risk and uncertainties and keeping harmony with environment. This system of farming is very promising for improving overall farm productivity, profitability, generating employment opportunities, conserving natural resources and maintains the sustainability of agro-ecosystem by effective recycling the farm by-products and efficient utilization of available resources. Integrating Farming System is the unique approach for overall upliftment of rural community and conserving the natural resources and crop diversity.

Women empowerment

Parveena belongs to lower middle-class family of Syedpora Harwan, Srinagar. After completing 12th, she could not continue her studies due to poverty and started her traditional occupation of agriculture. Resources possessed by the family were one hectare of land (0.5 irrigated and 0.5 rainfed), Cows (04), Poultry Unit (400 birds), Vermicomposting Unit (01), Polyhouse (01). Krishi Vighyan Kendra, Srinagar provided scientific training and pruning of fruit trees, Seed of high yielding varieties of vegetables along with their package of practices, training on cultivation of different vegetables and fruit crops, integrated nutrient management, composting of agriculture/ farm waste, poultry and dairy rearing and disease management, value addition of fruit and vegetables etc. Contributing factors for success of Parveena were her innovative mind, eagerness to learn new technologies, her parents and KVK and Deptt. Of Agriculture and Horticulture by providing inputs, technologies training, demonstration, disease diagnostic visit, marketing etc. To recognize her efforts in the field of IFS Parveena was awarded with a cash prize of Rs 8000 on 16/03/2019 and a cash prize of Rs. 5000 as president of SHG Zone Harwan during 2018-2019 from Department of Agriculture Kashmir. Parveena being the innovative Women farmer have become an inspiration to other farmers of nearby Villages by adopting Integrated farming systems. Her success influenced neighboring farmers so much that many of them have adopted the IFS models in their farms. Adjacent villages covered by the enterprise are Darbagh, Muftibagh, Dara, New Theed, Danhama.

Highlights of success

Parveena has created a self-help group (SHG Pari) having 10 members wherein she is active as a president of the group. Parveena earns a handsome return of more than 08 lac/annum and with the help of KVK she has been promoted as one of the key trainer on integrated farming system in the area and is giving training to the other farmers interested in integrated farming system.

